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Correlation Between Grain Size Distribution of Sedimentary Formations and Electrical Resistivity Investigation Results: Case of the Jacqueline Department (Côte d'Ivoire)

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between the grain size characteristics of sedimentary deposits and geoelectric properties in the Jacqueline department, located on the southern coastline of Côte d'Ivoire. The primary objective is to assess the influence of grain size distribution on the electrical response of sedimentary formations in order to improve their geological and hydrogeological characterization.

To achieve this objective, an integrated approach combining geophysical investigations and grain size analyses was implemented. The geophysical investigations consisted of six electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) profiles using a Dipole–Dipole array, distributed between the villages of N'djem and Abreby. The profiles, 245 m in length with an inter-electrode spacing of 5 m, allowed an investigation depth of approximately 145 m to be reached. In addition, six vertical electrical soundings (VES) using the Schlumberger array were carried out and interpreted using the IP2Win software. Furthermore, fifty-five samples collected at one-meter intervals between 1 and 55 m depth in a borehole were subjected to grain size analyses, enabling the determination of the D10, D30, D50, and D60 parameters, as well as the uniformity coefficient (Cu) and curvature coefficient (Cc).

The results reveal considerable grain size and geoelectric variability within the studied sedimentary formations. Correlation analyses indicate weak relationships between electrical resistivity and grain size parameters, with Pearson coefficients of -0.224 for D50, -0.185 for Cu, and -0.200 for Cc. These low correlations suggest that grain size is not the primary factor controlling the electrical response of the subsurface. Resistivity variations appear to be more strongly influenced by factors such as clay content, water saturation, pore fluid salinity, and lithological heterogeneity.

This study highlights the complexity of the relationships between textural and electrical properties in coastal sedimentary environments. It underscores the value of a multidisciplinary approach integrating grain size, geophysical, and hydrogeological data for a more comprehensive understanding of the aquifer systems within the Jacqueline sedimentary basin.

Keywords : *Jacqueline, grain size analysis, electrical resistivity tomography, vertical electrical sounding, coastal aquifer, sediment*

1. Introduction

Sedimentary formations constitute major aquifer reservoirs in many coastal regions of the world. Their hydrodynamic and geophysical properties are strongly influenced by the grain size characteristics of the constituent materials. Grain size distribution, defined as the distribution of particle sizes in a soil or loose rock, plays a fundamental role in controlling porosity, permeability, and fluid circulation within geological formations (Freeze and Cherry, 1979). Knowledge of these parameters is essential for the sustainable management of groundwater resources, particularly in coastal areas subject to increasing anthropogenic pressure.

Among subsurface investigation methods, electrical resistivity is widely used for the characterization of geological and hydrogeological formations. This technique is based on measuring the capacity of materials to resist the flow of electric current. Resistivity values depend on several factors, including lithological composition, water content, pore fluid salinity, porosity, and grain size of the materials (Archie, 1942 ; Keller and Frischknecht, 1966). Thus, coarse-grained deposits such as sands and gravels generally exhibit different electrical behaviors compared to fine-grained formations rich in silt or clay, owing to differences in porosity and surface conductivity.

The relationships between grain size properties and electrical parameters have been the subject of numerous studies aimed at improving the interpretation of geophysical data. According to Archie (1942), the resistivity of saturated porous formations is closely related to their porosity, which itself largely depends on the grain size distribution of the sediments. Furthermore, the work of Revil and Glover (1998) demonstrated that grain size and the presence of clay particles significantly influence electrical conduction mechanisms in porous media. The combined analysis of grain size and geoelectric data thus appears to be a relevant approach for better understanding the structure and properties of sedimentary aquifers.

The Jacqueline department, located on the coastline of Côte d'Ivoire, belongs to the Ivorian coastal sedimentary basin, characterized by a succession of sandy, clayey, and lagoonal formations. This region is experiencing significant demographic and economic growth that increases demand for groundwater resources. However, the lithological complexity of the sedimentary deposits sometimes makes it difficult to interpret geophysical results obtained by the electrical resistivity method. In this context, studying the relationship between the grain size of sedimentary deposits and electrical resistivity parameters represents a major scientific challenge for improving aquifer characterization and optimizing hydrogeological investigations.

The present study thus aims to analyze the influence of the grain size distribution of sedimentary deposits on electrical resistivity parameters in the Jacqueline department. Its objective is to establish correlations between the grain size characteristics of the encountered formations and the observed geoelectric responses in order to improve the interpretation of resistivity data and the understanding of the hydrogeological functioning of the study area.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

The study area encompasses the rural sectors of N'Djem and Abreby, bounded to the north by the Ebrié Lagoon and to the south by the Atlantic Ocean. It belongs to the Jacqueline department, within the coastal sedimentary basin of Côte d'Ivoire. The area is delimited by geographic coordinates ranging from 5°13'12" to 5°16'12" North latitude, and from 4°15'00" to 4°13'12" West longitude (Figure 1).

The study sector is characterized by a transitional equatorial climate marked by the alternation of four distinct seasons (Kouassi, 2013): a long wet season (May–July), a short dry season (August–September), a short wet season (October–November), and a long dry season (December–April). The topography is relatively uniform, dominated by a gently undulating plain. From a geological standpoint, the outcropping formations belong essentially to the Quaternary and consist of clayey sands and coarse

sands organized into coastal ridges. These deposits contain a freshwater water table, commonly referred to as the Quaternary aquifer (Douagui, 2012).

Figure 1 : Location of the study area

2.2 Geophysical Data Acquisition

2.2.1 Electrical Resistivity Tomography

The geophysical investigation was carried out using the electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) method, widely applied for two-dimensional imaging of subsurface structures and the characterization of geological and hydrogeological formations. This method is based on measuring the spatial variations in electrical resistivity of subsurface materials (Comte, 2008).

A total of six ERT profiles were conducted in the study area. Three parallel profiles were established in the northern part of the site, at the village of N'djem, while three additional parallel profiles were implemented in the southern part, at the village of Abreby. This configuration enabled representative spatial coverage of the main geological units encountered in the study sector, and allowed for the identification of potential lateral variations in the electrical properties of the subsurface.

Measurements were performed using the Dipole–Dipole configuration, recognized for its sensitivity to lateral resistivity variations and its ability to detect geological discontinuities, tectonic structures, and lithological variations. Each profile has a total length of 245 m with an inter-electrode spacing of 5 m. This array allowed a maximum investigation depth of approximately 145 m, thereby ensuring exploration of the principal geological and aquifer horizons in the study area.

The apparent resistivity data acquired in the field were processed using numerical inversion with the Res2DInv software. This software applies a least-squares inversion method to transform apparent resistivity measurements into two-dimensional models of true subsurface resistivity. The inversion process minimizes the discrepancy between observed and calculated data, yielding geoelectric cross-sections representative of the resistivity distribution with depth.

The resulting inverted cross-sections were interpreted in conjunction with available lithological information and grain size results in order to identify the different sedimentary units, characterize their spatial extent, and evaluate the influence of grain size distribution on the electrical properties of the formations encountered at the experimental site.

Figure 2 : ERT profile locations

2.2.2 Vertical Electrical Soundings (VES)

Complementing the electrical resistivity tomography investigations, a campaign of vertical electrical soundings (VES) was carried out to characterize the vertical variations in the electrical properties of the subsurface and to define the geometry of the various geological layers present in the study area.

A total of six electrical soundings were performed across the study site. Their locations were selected to ensure representative coverage of the main geological units identified and to allow correlation with both the ERT results and the grain size data.

Measurements were carried out using the Schlumberger array, widely employed in hydrogeological studies for its high sensitivity to vertical resistivity variations and its ability to investigate deep formations (Kouadio, 2021). In this configuration, the current electrodes (A and B) are progressively moved apart from the center of the array while the potential electrodes (M and N) remain relatively close together. This arrangement provides better resolution of vertical structures while limiting the number of potential electrode displacements during measurements.

Successive expansions of the array allowed a maximum investigation depth of approximately 150 m. The resulting apparent resistivity values were plotted as sounding curves representing the variation of resistivity as a function of the current electrode spacing.

Quantitative interpretation of the sounding curves was performed using the IP2Win software. This software uses an automatic and interactive inversion process to determine the geoelectric parameters of the different subsurface layers, in particular their true resistivity and thickness. The resulting geoelectric models were then compared with the ERT results and grain size data to improve the lithological identification of sedimentary formations and to better understand the relationships between grain size characteristics and the electrical properties of the deposits encountered at the experimental site.

Figure 3 : Location of the vertical electrical soundings

2.3 Grain Size Analysis

In order to characterize the textural properties of the sedimentary formations and assess their influence on geoelectric parameters, a sampling campaign was carried out using a hydrogeological drilling rig at the study site. Samples were collected using a systematic approach based on the depth-logging of drill cuttings, enabling a detailed description of the vertical variation in sedimentary facies.

A total of fifty-five (55) samples were collected from the surface to a depth of 55 m, at a rate of one sample per meter. This sampling strategy ensured continuous coverage of the sedimentary column and allowed the grain size variations associated with the different geological horizons encountered to be identified.

The collected samples were subsequently prepared in the laboratory by drying, homogenization, and disaggregation of aggregates to ensure the representativeness of the analyses. Grain size analyses were performed by mechanical sieving in accordance with standardized procedures used for the characterization of sedimentary materials. This method involves separating particles according to size using a series of sieves with progressively decreasing mesh sizes.

The results allowed the distribution of the different grain size fractions to be determined, including gravels, coarse sands, medium sands, fine sands, and fine-grained particles (silts and clays). From the cumulative grain size curves, several parameters were calculated, including the characteristic diameters (D10, D30, D50, and D60), the uniformity coefficient (Cu), and the curvature coefficient (Cc), which are commonly used for the characterization of porous media.

Interpretation of the grain size data enabled the identification of vertical variations in sedimentary deposits and the distinction of different facies present in the study area. These results were then compared with resistivity data from electrical resistivity tomography and vertical electrical soundings in order to establish correlations between sediment texture and electrical properties. This integrated approach contributes to a better understanding of the influence of grain size distribution on the geoelectric response of sedimentary formations in the Jacqueville department.

2.4 Correlation Between Grain Size and Geoelectric Data

The analysis of the relationship between the grain size characteristics of sedimentary deposits and their electrical properties was performed by integrating the grain size data obtained from the collected samples with the resistivity data derived from the vertical electrical soundings (VES) and electrical resistivity tomography (ERT).

2.4.1 Data Harmonization

The first step involved establishing a correspondence between the grain size sampling depths and the geoelectric horizons identified during the interpretation of the VES and ERT profiles. Resistivity values assigned to each sampling level were extracted from the inverted geoelectric models.

For each depth investigated, a database combining grain size and electrical parameters was compiled. This database includes:

- Sampling depth (m);
- Electrical resistivity ($\Omega \cdot m$);
- Characteristic grain size diameters;
- Uniformity coefficient (C_u);
- Curvature coefficient (C_c).

2.4.2 Descriptive Analysis

A descriptive statistical analysis was conducted to characterize the distribution of grain size and geoelectric parameters. Minimum, maximum, mean, median, and standard deviation values were calculated for all studied variables.

2.4.3 Correlation Analysis

The relationships between grain size parameters and electrical resistivities were assessed using correlation analyses. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was used to measure the strength and direction of linear relationships between the variables :

- Resistivity versus D50;
- Resistivity versus D10;
- Resistivity versus uniformity coefficient (C_u).

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- X_i = value of variable X (e.g., D50);
- Y_i = value of variable Y (e.g., resistivity);
- \bar{x} = mean of X;
- \bar{y} = mean of Y;
- n = number of observations.

The values of the correlation coefficient were interpreted according to the classification proposed by Mukaka (2012) :

- $|r| < 0.30$: weak correlation;
- $0.30 \leq |r| < 0.50$: moderate correlation;

- $0.50 \leq |r| < 0.70$: strong correlation;
- $|r| \geq 0.70$: very strong correlation.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Results

3.1.1 Electrical Resistivity Tomography Results

The six ERT profiles (Figures 3 and 4) generated inversion models with low absolute errors of 3.0%, 4.9%, and 4.52% for the northern profiles, and 8.2%, 11.8%, and 5.4% for the southern profiles, attesting to the reliability of the measurements.

Interpretation of the geoelectric models reveals a stratified structure composed of three main units. The first unit is characterized by high resistivities ranging from 474 Ω·m to 1,186 Ω·m, extending to a depth of approximately 18 m. It corresponds essentially to sandy formations, including dry, medium, and coarse sands. The second unit exhibits intermediate resistivities varying from 30 Ω·m to 200 Ω·m. Located below the first horizon, it extends to approximately 60 m depth and is associated with clayey sand and clay formations. Finally, the third unit is characterized by low resistivities of less than 12 Ω·m. It consists of sands and/or clays whose low resistivity values reflect high mineralization linked to saline water intrusion.

Figure 4: 2D ERT profiles conducted in the northern part of the site (N'Djem village)

Figure 5 : 2D ERT profiles conducted in the southern part of the site (Abreby village)

3.1.2 Vertical Electrical Sounding Results

The sounding curves display a similar descending pattern (Figure 6). This pattern highlights three geological units defined by their resistivity values (illustrated on VES 1) :

- Unit 1 : Resistivity values ranging from approximately 700 $\Omega \cdot m$ to approximately 1,800 $\Omega \cdot m$, indicating the presence of geological formations such as dry, medium, or coarse sand;
- Unit 2 : Resistivity values oscillating between 600 $\Omega \cdot m$ and 70 $\Omega \cdot m$, marking the presence of clayey sand and clay;

- Unit 3 : Resistivity values below $30 \Omega \cdot m$. The formations present may consist of either clay or sand; the low values result from saturation with saline water.

Figure 6 : Vertical electrical soundings

3.1.3 Grain Size Analysis Results

3.1.3.1 Global Statistical Parameters

Grain size analysis of the 55 levels sampled in the borehole, carried out according to the Folk and Ward (1957) method, yielded the four statistical indicators summarized in the table below :

Table 1 : Global statistical parameters of grain size distribution

Parameter	Minimum (Φ)	Maximum (Φ)	Mean (Φ)	Median (Φ)
Mz — Mean grain size	-0.440	+1.644	+0.452	+0.421
σI — Sorting	0.514	1.695	0.964	0.924
SkI — Skewness	-0.321	+0.505	+0.163	+0.171
KG — Kurtosis	0.540	1.896	1.137	1.087

Mean Mz = +0.452 Φ : Dominant coarse sand

Mean σI = 0.964 Φ : Moderately sorted

Mean SkI = +0.163 : Fine-skewed

Mean KG = 1.137 : Leptokurtic

3.1.3.2 Grain Size Classes

The mean grain size Mz ranges from -0.440 Φ (very coarse sand, level 39 m) to +1.644 Φ (medium sand, level 1 m). According to the Wentworth (1922) classification, three classes are represented:

Table 2: Grain size classes

Grain size class	Levels (n)	Proportion (%)	Typical Mz Φ	Representative depths
Coarse sand (500–250 μm)	36	65.5	+0.42 to +0.97	2–10, 12, 13, 18–25, 33–38, 42–55 m
Very coarse sand (1000–500 μm)	14	25.5	-0.44 to +0.01	11, 14, 17, 29–32, 39–41 m
Medium sand (250–125 μm)	5	9.1	+1.00 to +1.64	1, 21, 26, 28, 43 m

3.1.3.3 Skewness (SkI)

Skewness ranges from -0.321 (level 23 m, very coarse-skewed) to +0.505 (level 1 m, very fine-skewed). The majority of levels exhibit positive skewness:

Table 3 : Skewness classes (SkI)

Skewness class	Levels (n)	Proportion (%)
Very fine-skewed (SkI > +0.30)	12	21.8
Fine-skewed (+0.10 to +0.30)	26	47.3
Symmetrical (-0.10 to +0.10)	14	25.5
Coarse-skewed (-0.30 to -0.10)	2	3.6
Very coarse-skewed (< -0.30)	1	1.8

In total, 69.1% of the levels exhibit positive skewness (SkI > 0), and only 5.4% exhibit negative skewness. Three levels record notable negative skewness: 9 m (SkI = -0.240), 23 m (SkI = -0.321), and 46 m (SkI = -0.252).

3.1.3.4 Kurtosis (KG)

Kurtosis ranges from 0.540 (very platykurtic, level 1 m) to 1.896 (very leptokurtic, level 39 m). Leptokurtic and mesokurtic distributions are dominant :

Table 4 : Kurtosis classes

Kurtosis class	KG range	Levels (n)	Proportion (%)
Very platykurtic	< 0.67	1	1.8
Platykurtic	0.67 – 0.90	13	23.6
Mesokurtic	0.90 – 1.11	15	27.3
Leptokurtic	1.11 – 1.50	19	34.5
Very leptokurtic	> 1.50	7	12.7

3.1.3.5 Interpretation of the Grain Size Curve

The grain size curves show that the majority of samples are dominated by sandy fractions with a low proportion of fine-grained particles (Figure 7). The curves generally display a relatively steep slope in the intermediate grain size classes, indicating a predominance of medium to coarse sands. However, some flatter curves suggest the local presence of finer or poorly sorted materials.

Figure 7 : Grain size curve of the Jacqueville Quaternary aquifer

These results reflect the complexity of the sedimentary environments encountered in the coastal zone of Jacqueville.

Figure 9 : Illustration of D50, Cu, and Cc as a function of depth

3.1.4 Correlation Between Grain Size Parameters and Electrical Resistivity

The Pearson correlation coefficients calculated between grain size parameters and electrical resistivities are presented in the following table :

Table 4 : Correlation between grain size parameters and resistivity

Variable	Pearson r	R ²
D50	-0.224	0.050
Cu	-0.185	0.034
Cc	-0.200	0.040

3.1.4.1 Variation in Resistivity with Depth

Analysis of the resistivity–depth profile (Figure 10) reveals considerable variability in the electrical properties of the studied sedimentary formations. Resistivity values exhibit substantial fluctuations with depth, reflecting a lithological heterogeneity characteristic of coastal sedimentary environments.

High resistivities observed in certain horizons may be associated with relatively clean, well-drained sandy formations. Conversely, resistivity decreases recorded at certain depths suggest the presence of finer materials, such as clayey sands or clay-rich levels, whose conductivity is enhanced by surface conduction phenomena. This vertical variability also reflects changes in depositional conditions and hydrogeological contrasts within the sedimentary basin of the study area.

The depth-dependent evolution of resistivity thus highlights a succession of layers with distinct physical properties, confirming the observations derived from grain size analyses.

Figure 10 : Resistivity profile as a function of depth

3.1.4.2 Relationship Between Electrical Resistivity and Median Diameter (D50)

such as water The resistivity–D50 graph shows considerable scatter in the experimental data points and the absence of a clearly defined linear trend. The Pearson correlation coefficient obtained ($r = -0.224$) indicates a weak negative correlation between resistivity and the median particle diameter.

The associated coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.050$) shows that only 5% of the resistivity variability can be explained by variations in D50. This low value suggests that mean grain size does not constitute the primary factor controlling the electrical response of the studied formations.

In sedimentary media, an increase in grain size is generally associated with an increase in resistivity due to a decrease in specific surface area and surface conductivity. However, this theoretical relationship may be masked by the influence of other parameters content, pore fluid salinity, and the presence of clay materials. The results obtained suggest that these factors likely exert a greater influence than median grain size in the study area.

Figure 11 : Relationship between electrical resistivity and median diameter (D50)

3.1.4.3 Relationship Between Electrical Resistivity and Uniformity Coefficient (Cu)

The comparison between resistivity and the uniformity coefficient also shows considerable data scatter. The calculated correlation coefficient ($r = -0.185$) indicates a very weak negative correlation between these two variables.

The low value of the coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.034$) indicates that only 3.4% of the resistivity variations are explained by variations in the uniformity coefficient. This result suggests that the degree of grain size sorting exerts a limited influence on the electrical properties of the studied formations.

In sedimentary deposits, high Cu values generally reflect a wide distribution of grain sizes and may promote a decrease in effective porosity through infilling of voids by fine particles. However, in the present case, the absence of a significant relationship indicates that effects related to the mineralogical composition and hydrogeological characteristics of the medium probably dominate over the influence of grain size sorting.

Figure 12 : Relationship between electrical resistivity and uniformity coefficient (Cu)

3.1.4.4 Relationship Between Electrical Resistivity and Curvature Coefficient (Cc)

The resistivity–Cc graph also displays considerable scatter. The Pearson coefficient obtained ($r = -0.200$) indicates a weak negative correlation between resistivity and the curvature coefficient.

The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.040$) shows that only 4% of the resistivity variations can be attributed to variations in Cc. This low contribution reflects the limited influence of the shape of the grain size distribution on the electrical properties of the subsurface.

The low correlation values obtained for Cu and Cc suggest that the parameters describing sediment sorting and grading are insufficient, on their own, to account for the resistivity variations observed in the formations of the study area.

Figure 13 : Relationship between electrical resistivity and curvature coefficient (Cc)

4. Discussion

Analysis of the relationships between grain size parameters and electrical resistivities reveals weak correlations between resistivity and D50 ($r = -0.224$), Cu ($r = -0.185$), and Cc ($r = -0.200$). Although these results reflect the limited influence of grain size on the observed resistivity values, they primarily highlight the complexity of the mechanisms controlling the electrical properties of coastal sedimentary deposits.

In sandy formations, electrical resistivity is generally influenced by grain size, porosity, and the connectivity of the porous network. An increase in particle size is often associated with a decrease in specific surface area and an increase in electrical resistivity (Binley and Kemna, 2005 ; Slater, 2007). However, in coastal aquifers, this theoretical relationship is frequently disrupted by the physicochemical quality of groundwater and local lithological variations.

The weak correlations observed in the Jacquville area may be attributed to the dominant influence of water saturation and pore fluid mineralization. Several recent studies have shown that in coastal aquifer systems subject to saltwater intrusion, electrical conductivity is more strongly controlled by water salinity than by the textural properties of the porous medium (Werner et al., 2013 ; Beaujean et al., 2014 ; Goebel et al., 2017). In this context, relatively coarse sandy formations may exhibit low resistivities when saturated by brackish or saline water.

The weak correlation obtained with the median diameter D50 suggests that mean grain size is not a major discriminating factor at the scale of the entire site. This observation is consistent with the findings of Comas et al. (2012), who showed that relationships between grain size and resistivity often become non-linear in heterogeneous environments where multiple geological factors interact simultaneously.

Moreover, the uniformity coefficient (Cu) and curvature coefficient (Cc) showed no significant relationship with the measured resistivities. This can be explained by the fact that these parameters essentially describe the degree of sediment sorting, whereas the electrical response depends more on the mineralogical nature of fine particles and the characteristics of the pore fluids. According to Revil and Florsch (2010), even low proportions of clay can substantially alter the electrical conductivity of a porous medium due to surface conduction phenomena associated with clay minerals.

The results also suggest significant heterogeneity in the sedimentary deposits of Jacquville. The ERT profiles conducted in the villages of N'djem and Abreby revealed significant lateral resistivity variations, reflecting the alternation of sandy, sandy-clay, and clay layers. This spatial heterogeneity likely contributes to the scatter observed in the resistivity–D50, resistivity–Cu, and resistivity–Cc plots.

Furthermore, the grain size data were derived from a single borehole, whereas the geoelectric data represent an integrated response over a larger volume of the subsurface. This difference in observation scale may attenuate the statistical relationships between the two types of data. Similar conclusions were reported by Uhlemann et al. (2017), who emphasize the need to integrate geological, hydrogeological, and geophysical data at multiple scales to improve the interpretation of aquifer properties.

Thus, the low correlation coefficients obtained do not negate the existence of an influence of grain size on the electrical properties of the studied formations. Rather, they indicate that this influence is masked by other dominant factors, including groundwater salinity, clay content, water saturation, and lithological heterogeneity. In the context of the Jacquville coastal sedimentary basin, electrical resistivity thus appears to result from a complex interaction between the textural characteristics of the deposits and the hydrogeological conditions of the medium.

These results confirm the value of an integrated approach combining grain size analyses, geoelectric data, and hydrochemical parameters in order to better understand the functioning of coastal aquifers and the mechanisms controlling their geophysical response.

5. Conclusion

The present study aimed to assess the influence of the grain size distribution of sedimentary deposits on electrical resistivity parameters in the Jacquville department, using an integrated approach combining electrical resistivity tomography, vertical electrical soundings, and grain size analyses.

The geophysical investigations carried out revealed significant heterogeneity in the subsurface formations, characterized by the alternation of sandy, sandy-clay, and clay layers. The ERT profiles and vertical electrical soundings revealed considerable resistivity variations both vertically and laterally, reflecting the geological and hydrogeological complexity of the Jacquville coastal sedimentary basin.

Grain size analyses performed on the fifty-five samples collected between 1 and 55 m depth showed a predominance of sandy materials with varying degrees of sorting across the horizons. The calculated grain size parameters (D10, D30, D50, D60, Cu, and Cc) enabled the characterization of deposit texture and highlighted variations in sedimentation conditions within the study area.

Comparison of grain size and geoelectric data showed that correlations between textural parameters and electrical resistivities remain relatively weak. The Pearson coefficients obtained indicate that resistivity variations cannot be explained solely by grain size or the degree of sediment sorting. These results suggest that other parameters play a determining role in the electrical response of the formations, including clay content, porosity, degree of saturation, and pore water conductivity.

In the particular context of the Jacquville coastal aquifers, the potential influence of brackish or saline water appears as a major factor liable to alter the electrical properties of the formations and to mask purely grain size-related effects. The results thus confirm that electrical resistivity constitutes an integrative parameter reflecting the combined action of multiple geological and hydrogeological factors.

Despite the weak statistical correlations observed, this study demonstrates the value of geophysical methods for characterizing sedimentary formations and understanding subsurface organization. The combination of geoelectric and grain size data has improved the interpretation of geological structures

and contributed to a better understanding of the mechanisms controlling the physical properties of the aquifers.

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